

Tutorial for the use of the “CovidAssociations” package

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1. INTRODUCTION

The “CovidAssociations” package contains results from the analysis of associations between variables in a large cohort of Mexican patients, which full results will be submitted for publication soon (Martínez, 2023). This tutorial will practically show how to use the package to [data mining](#) these results¹.

I assume that you have some practical knowledge in the use of the [R Project for Statistical Computing](#) (R Core Team, 2022). This tutorial will give you an step-by-step guide to use the package, using text “Boxes” where both, the orders pass to R in the command line, as well as the results given by the program will be shown. In such boxes the text immediately following the prompt, “>” is the R command (just copy and paste the R command that is AFTER the prompt), while the rows following give the results, exactly as you will see them in your command window. As usual, lines that begin with a remark sign, “#”, are comments that will be ignored by R, but that will help you to understand what is going on.

Box 1 gives the command to install and load the package. You can omit the install command if you have already installed the package.

```
-----  
# Box 1. Installing and loading  
# Note: You must have file "CovidAssociations_1.0.tar.gz" in your working directory  
> install.packages("CovidAssociations_1.0.tar.gz", repos = NULL, type="source")  
# some stuff will be printed...  
  
# Now, load the library [Needed for all other boxes to work!]  
> library(CovidAssociations)  
> ? CovidAssociations # Get help about the package  
  
? var.desc # Help for that data.frame  
> head(var.desc, 2) # Two rows of that data.frame  
      Name Abbr   Category  
1      asthma  as Comorbidity  
2 cardiovascular  ca Comorbidity  
  
                                     Description  
1      logical; patient reported to be suffering from asthma.  
2      logical; patient reported to be suffering cardiovascular problems.  
  
> ? all.res # Help about that data.frame  
> dim(all.res) # Rows and columns  
[1] 3899  18  
> names(all.res) # Names of the variables  
[1] "n.tab"      "n.c.row"    "n.c.col"    "name.row"   "name.col"  
[6] "name.tab"   "pv"         "or"         "LL"         "UL"
```

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¹Text in blue are linked to a relevant web site, if you want to further explore the subject.

```
[11] "or2"      "dir"      "came.from" "tab.file" "a"
[16] "b"        "c"        "d"
> summary(all.res$or) # Summary of Odds Ratios (or variable)
  Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
 0.000  1.121   1.851   8.761  4.177 4655.848
> summary(all.res$pv) # Summary of p-values in Fisher's exact test (pv variable)
  Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
0.00000 0.00000 0.00000 0.03568 0.00000 1.00000
# You could also see the histograms for those variables (not shown here)
# > hist(log10(all.res$or+1)) # Transformed to make sense
# > hist(all.res$pv)
```

2. DATA MINING "PREGNANCY" ASSOCIATIONS

The "all.res" data frame contains the results from the [Fisher's exact test](#) for 3,899 pairs of variables in different patient's sets. However, those results are not straightly interpretable; not knowledge can be directly infer from such large data collection without having a particular focus in mind.

Here we will assume that you are interested in exploring associations found in the cohort when one of the variables of interest is "pregnancy". Let's begin by isolating the results which include "pregnancy" and any other variable in the set of all patients. See and follow the steps in [Box 2](#).

```
# Box 2. Isolating results where pregnancy is involved
> ? isolate.res # Help for that function

# Let's begin by making a mistake:
> isolate.res("pregnant") # Will fail...
var1 = "pregnant" is not valid.
Permissible values are:
asthma, cardiovascular, chr.renal, copd, deceased, diabetes, gender, hospitalized,
hypertension, icu, imm.suppl, indigenous, intubated, mexican, obesity, other.com,
pneumonia, pos.cov2, pregnancy, smoking,

(a single value within "").
Example: var1="asthma"
Error in isolate.res("pregnant"): 'var1' must be a valid variable.

# OK; now we know that the correct name is "pregnancy".
# Let's call the function and assign the result to "pre1"
> pre1 <- isolate.res("pregnancy")
> class(pre1)
[1] "data.frame"
> dim(pre1) # Rows and columns
[1] 18 15
> names(pre1) # Names of variables included
 [1] "name.row"  "name.col"  "name.tab"  "pv"        "or"
 [6] "LL"       "UL"       "or2"      "dir"      "came.from"
[11] "tab.file"  "a"        "b"        "c"        "d"
```

Note: in isolate.res("pregnancy") we implicitly used the defaults for various parameters, i.e., the statement

```

# pre1 <- isolate.res("pregnancy") is equivalent to
# pre1 <- isolate.res(var1="pregnancy", var2 = NULL,
# only.significant = FALSE, alpha = 0.01, group = "gen.res")
# In particular, group = "gen.res" means that we are selecting as
# target group the set of all patients (without restrictions), see:
> ? came.from.desc # Help for that data.frame
> came.from.desc[came.from.desc$came.from=="gen.res",] # Relevant row
  came.from n.res      Description
1  gen.res   187 General (gen); all patients.

> head(pre1, 2) # See the fist two rows of pre1
  name.row name.col      name.tab pv      or      LL
1  deceased pregnancy deceased_pregnancy 0 0.1350388 0.1239381
2  pregnancy  copd      pregnancy_copd 0 0.1732362 0.1549535
      UL      or2      dir came.from tab.file      a      b
1 0.1468396 7.405282 35_General  gen.res  gen.tab 13522638 296538
2 0.1930159 5.772466 35_General  gen.res  gen.tab 13595353 87092
      c      d
1 185759 550
2 296496 329

# To begin to understand we could order the data by or (Odds Ratio)
> pre1 <- pre1[order(pre1$or), ] # Ordered in increasing order of Odds Ratio (or)
> attributes(pre1)$row.names <- c(1:18) # Rename the rows

> pre1[,3:5] # See main results
      name.tab      pv      or
1  deceased_pregnancy 0.000000e+00 0.1350388
2  pregnancy_copd 0.000000e+00 0.1732362
3  pregnancy_hypertension 0.000000e+00 0.2005781
4  pregnancy_chr.renal 0.000000e+00 0.2320866
5  intubated_pregnancy 0.000000e+00 0.2591968
6  pregnancy_diabetes 0.000000e+00 0.2812515
7  pregnancy_cardiovascular 0.000000e+00 0.2826362
8  pregnancy_smoking 0.000000e+00 0.3569136
9  pregnancy_obesity 0.000000e+00 0.5252757
10 pregnancy_imm.sup 4.723614e-87 0.5662802
11 pos.cov2_pregnancy 0.000000e+00 0.6176913
12 pregnancy_asthma 3.159774e-186 0.6693361
13 icu_pregnancy 1.502839e-41 0.6821157
14 pneumonia_pregnancy 2.442184e-134 0.7391638
15 mexican_pregnancy 5.592634e-04 1.0904143
16 pregnancy_other.com 6.005580e-79 1.3110133
17 hospitalized_pregnancy 0.000000e+00 2.2548974
18 indigenous_pregnancy 0.000000e+00 3.3548929

> summary(pre1[,4:5]) # Summaries of Odds Ratio (or) and p-values (pv)
      pv      or
Min.   :0.000e+00  Min.   :0.1350
1st Qu.:0.000e+00  1st Qu.:0.2647
Median :0.000e+00  Median :0.5458
Mean   :3.107e-05  Mean   :0.7629

```

```
3rd Qu.:0.000e+00  3rd Qu.:0.7249
Max.      :5.593e-04  Max.      :3.3549
```

In Box 2 we see that there are results from 18 tables involving “pregnancy”. The Odds Ratios (“or”) which measure the association between the tabulated variables go from a minimum of 0.1350 to a maximum of 3.3549 and all those 18 results are statistically “*significant*” given that the maximum p -value is $5.593e - 04 = 5.593 \times 10^{-4} = 0.0005593$. This high significance is due to the fact that very large sample sizes exist in the tables, and thus even very small deviations from the neutral Odds Ratio of 1 are “*significant*”; i.e., we have that the test has high [statistical power](#).

To be able to correctly interpret the results it is vital to have a good understanding of the concept of [Odds ratio](#), which is used here to measure the observed association between variables. In particular a value of $or \approx 1$ means that there is small association between the variables, while the extremes $or = 0$ and $or = \text{Inf}$ (infinite, does not found in our data) will mean an strong inverse and direct relation, respectively.

Box 3 presents the results for the table with the smallest Odds Ratio ($or = 0.13504$) found in `pre1`. That table is obtained using the function “`present.table()`”.

```
# Box 3. Using present.table() to interpret an extreme case in pre1.
# (the table found with the minimum or).

> ? present.table # See the help for that function
> pre1[1,] # First row, with the smallest or
  name.row name.col      name.tab pv      or      LL      UL
1 deceased pregnancy deceased_pregnancy 0 0.1350388 0.1239381 0.1468396
  or2      dir came.from tab.file      a      b      c      d
1 7.405282 35_General  gen.res  gen.tab 13522638 296538 185759 550

# See those results in an orderly way and keep the results
> temp <- present.table(pre1[1,])
```

Results for table of variable "deceased" (in rows)
and variable "pregnancy" (in columns).
Sufix ".T" after the variable name means "TRUE", while ".F" means "FALSE".
The data came from selecting variables in group "gen.res".

Raw data:

	pregnancy.F	pregnancy.T	Total.Row
deceased.F	13,522,638	296,538	13,819,176
deceased.T	185,759	550	186,309
Total.Col	13,708,397	297,088	14,005,485

Expected values assuming independence:

	pregnancy.F	pregnancy.T
deceased.F	13,526,040	293,136
deceased.T	182,357	3,952

Relative frequencies:

	pregnancy.F	pregnancy.T	Total.Row
deceased.F	0.96552	0.02117	0.9867
deceased.T	0.01326	0.00004	0.0133

```
Total.Col      0.97879      0.02121      1.0000
```

```
Conditional probabilities of row given column:
                pregnancy.F pregnancy.T
deceased.F | pregnancy      0.98645      0.99815
deceased.T | pregnancy      0.01355      0.00185
```

```
Conditional probabilities of column given row:
                deceased.F deceased.T
pregnancy.F | deceased      0.97854      0.99705
pregnancy.T | deceased      0.02146      0.00295
```

Results of Fisher's test for independence

```
Odds Ratio      p-value
      0.13504      0.00000
```

Inverse of Odds Ratio, $1/(\text{Odds Ratio}) = 7.40528$

```
# Also note that we have the results in "temp"
> class(temp) # Results
[1] "list"
> names(temp)
[1] "raw.tab"          "expected"          "raw.tab.wt"
[4] "rel.fre"          "cond.row.giv.col"  "cond.col.giv.row"
[7] "results.fisher.test" "the.row"
> temp$raw.tab # Raw data
                pregnancy.F pregnancy.T
deceased.F      13522638      296538
deceased.T       185759        550
> ? fisher.test # To see the details of that function.
> fisher.test(temp$raw.tab) # Redoing the analysis to check.
```

Fisher's Exact Test for Count Data

```
data: temp$raw.tab
p-value < 2.2e-16
alternative hypothesis: true oddsratio is not equal to 1
95 percent confidence interval:
 0.1239381 0.1468396
sample estimates:
odds ratio
 0.1350388
```

```
# Note: calculating the sample Odds Ratio "by hand"
# or = (a*d) / (b*c)
> temp$raw.tab
                pregnancy.F pregnancy.T
deceased.F      13522638      296538
deceased.T       185759        550
> (temp$raw.tab[1,1]*temp$raw.tab[2,2])/(temp$raw.tab[1,2]*temp$raw.tab[2,1])
[1] 0.1350187
# The small difference is because Fisher's test uses a Maximum Likelihood
```

approach to calculate Odds Ratio.

In Box 3 we can see how the first row of `pre1` is re-organized and presented in meaningful tables by function `present.table`. The `Raw data:` table shows how a total of 14,005,485 patients were classified in the 2×2 contingency table by the criteria `deceased` (FALSE or TRUE in rows) and `pregnancy` (FALSE or TRUE in columns). Note that the variables `a`, `b`, `c` and `d` in `pre[1,]` correspond to the values in the cells of `Raw data`.

The second table presented in Box 3 corresponds to the `Expected values assuming independence`, and comparing that with the previous table (`Raw data:`) we see that, while the observed value in the cell `deceased.T, pregnancy.T` is 550, the value expected for such cell under independence is 3,952, thus we have approximately 7.19 times less pregnant patients that died than the number expected if the two criteria were independent ($3,952/550 \approx 7.19$). Or, equivalently, we observe a proportion of only 0.00004 of pregnant patients that died, compared with the number expected under independence ($3952/14005485 \approx 0.0003$).

In general the Odds Ratio measures the relative likelihood of events from the information that we have in the table of raw data. In this case (`Raw data` in Box 3) we can measure the odds of surviving relative to pregnancy,

$$(\text{survived and not pregnant})/(\text{survived and pregnant}) = \frac{a}{b} = \frac{13,522,638}{296,538} \approx 45.6017$$

and also the odds of death relative to pregnancy

$$(\text{died and not pregnant})/(\text{died and pregnant}) = \frac{c}{d} = \frac{185,759}{550} \approx 337.7436$$

to finally calculate the *ratio* of those two quantities, i.e., the Odds Ratio,

$$\begin{aligned} & [(\text{survived and not pregnant})/(\text{survived and pregnant})] / [(\text{died and not pregnant})/(\text{died and pregnant})] \\ &= \left[\frac{a}{b}\right] / \left[\frac{c}{d}\right] = \frac{a \times d}{b \times c} \approx \frac{45.6017}{337.7436} = 0.1350187 \end{aligned}$$

which is almost equal to the value given by the Fisher's test: 0.1350388 The small difference arises from the fact that this function employs the *conditional* Maximum Likelihood Estimate, instead of the sample odds ratio.

Odds Ratios less than the neutral value of 1 are not directly interpretable (McHugh, 2009), thus in those cases it is better to take the inverse value, i.e., $1 / \text{Odds Ratio}$, that in the results given by the function `isolate.res()` is denoted as "`or2`". In this case we have that $1/0.1350187 \approx 7.4$ is easier to interpret and the interpretation is that it was approximately 7.4 times more likely to die in not pregnant patients than in pregnant ones, and one is tempted to conclude that, in some sense, pregnancy has a "*protective*" effect against death in Covid patients.

Also, in Box 2 we saw that in 14 of the 18 cases (78%, see `pre1[, 3:5]`) the value of the `or < 1`, and thus for all those 14 cases the odds of having the corresponding variable as "`TRUE`" when "`pregnancy == TRUE`" are smaller than the neutral value of 1 and also highly significant.

Also in Box 3 we can see the conditional probabilities. For example in the table "`Conditional probabilities of row given column`", we see that the probability of death in not pregnant persons was estimated to be 0.01355 (cell in the intersection of row "`deceased.T | pregnancy`" with column "`pregnancy.F`") , while in contrast the probability of death in pregnant persons was estimated to be only 0.00185 (cell in the intersection of row "`deceased.T | pregnancy`" with column "`pregnancy.T`"). This means that the relative risk of death in not pregnant when compared with pregnant persons is more than seven times higher ($0.01355/0.00185 \approx 7.3$).

Box 4 presents the tables with the highest Odds Ratio within the pairs of "`pregnancy`" with the other variables in the set of general results (group "`gen.res`").

```
# Box 4. Presenting the table with the highest or in pre1
> pre1[18, ] # The data that will be presented
  name.row name.col      name.tab pv      or      LL      UL
18 indigenous pregnancy indigenous_pregnancy 0 3.354893 3.272501 3.438902
  or2      dir came.from tab.file      a      b      c      d
18 3.354893 35_General gen.res gen.tab 12749188 270978 97073 6922
> present.table(pre1[18, ])
```

Results for table of variable "indigenous" (in rows)
and variable "pregnancy" (in columns).
Sufix ".T" after the variable name means "TRUE", while ".F" means "FALSE".
The data came from selecting variables in group "gen.res".

Raw data:

	pregnancy.F	pregnancy.T	Total.Row
indigenous.F	12,749,188	270,978	13,020,166
indigenous.T	97,073	6,922	103,995
Total.Col	12,846,261	277,900	13,124,161

Expected values assuming independence:

	pregnancy.F	pregnancy.T
indigenous.F	12,744,468	275,698
indigenous.T	101,793	2,202

Relative frequencies:

	pregnancy.F	pregnancy.T	Total.Row
indigenous.F	0.97143	0.02065	0.99208
indigenous.T	0.00740	0.00053	0.00792
Total.Col	0.97883	0.02117	1.00000

Conditional probabilities of row given column:

	pregnancy.F	pregnancy.T
indigenous.F pregnancy	0.99244	0.97509
indigenous.T pregnancy	0.00756	0.02491

Conditional probabilities of column given row:

	indigenous.F	indigenous.T
pregnancy.F indigenous	0.97919	0.93344
pregnancy.T indigenous	0.02081	0.06656

Results of Fisher's test for independence

Odds Ratio	p-value
3.35489	0.00000

From Box 4 we can see that the number of observed pregnant persons which are classified as "indigenous" in the data are 6,922, while the expected value for this cell under the criterion of independence is 2,202; i.e, we have more than three times the number of observed than expected, $6,922/2,202 \approx 3.14$ and thus there is an estimated Odds Ratio of ≈ 3.4

Also, from the table "Conditional probabilities of column given row:" within Box 4 we see that the conditional probability of finding a pregnant person which is classified as indigenous is 0.06656 while

the conditional probability of finding a pregnant person which is not classified as indigenous is 0.02081, i.e., the former is more than 3 times larger than the latter ($0.06656/0.02081 \approx 3.2$).

At this point it is important to take into account that the general results previously analyzed in boxes 2 to 4 include only the set of all patients (group "gen.res"), and not particular subsets of those groups. We will now, in Box 5, extend our group to include all groups of patients for which the variable "pregnancy" is paired (compared) with other variables.

```
-----
# Box 5. "pregnancy" in all different groups.
> pre2 <- isolate.res("pregnancy", group="all")
> nrow(pre2)
[1] 222
> names(pre2)
 [1] "name.row"  "name.col"  "name.tab"  "pv"        "or"        "LL"
 [7] "UL"        "or2"       "dir"       "came.from" "tab.file"  "a"
[13] "b"         "c"         "d"
> table(pre2$came.from) # How many in each group?

      ad.res      ch.res      dec.res dpy2020.res dpy2021.res dpy2022.res
      19         19          9          17          18          17
dpy2023.res  fem.res      gen.res      hos.res      ma.res      nho.res
      18         18         18         16         19         15
      te.res
      19
> summary(pre2[,4:5]) # Summaries of "pv" and "or"
      pv          or
Min.   :0.00000  Min.   :0.0000
1st Qu.:0.00000  1st Qu.:0.2592
Median :0.00000  Median :0.6125
Mean   :0.08826  Mean   :0.9608
3rd Qu.:0.00000  3rd Qu.:1.0904
Max.   :1.00000  Max.   :7.7850

# Given the complexity of these results, let's create a data.frame to organize
# the results by group of origin. We are interested mainly in the "or" per group
# of patients.

# Define a data.frame to keep the results:
> pre2.summ <- data.frame(Group="sort(unique(pre2$came.from))", Desc="", n=NA,
      Min.or=NA, Median.or=NA, Mean.or=NA, Max.or=NA)
> nrow(pre2.summ)
[1] 13

# Execute all the lines in the loop...
for(i in 1:13){
pre2.summ$n[i] <- nrow(pre2[pre2$came.from == pre2.summ$Group[i],])
pre2.summ$Desc[i] <- came.from.desc$Description[came.from.desc$came.from == pre2.summ$Group[i]]
pre2.summ[i, 4:7] <- summary(pre2$or[pre2$came.from == pre2.summ$Group[i]])[c(1,3,4,6)]
}

> pre2.summ <- pre2.summ[order(pre2.summ$Desc), ] # Reorder
> attributes(pre2.summ)$row.names <- c(1:13) # Rename rows
```

```
# Show a summary of results
> cbind(pre2.summ[,2], round(pre2.summ[,4:7], 2))
      pre2.summ[, 2] Min.or Median.or Mean.or Max.or
1   Age group adult (ad) from 20 to 39 years.  0.00   0.98   1.32   6.24
2   Age group child (ch) from 5 to 12 years.   0.00   0.80   1.61   7.79
3   Age group middle age (ma) from 40 to 59 years. 0.00   0.63   0.93   3.77
4   Age group teens (te) from 13 to 19 years.  0.00   0.79   1.42   5.41
5                               Data for year 2020. 0.15   0.47   0.76   2.91
6                               Data for year 2021. 0.16   0.58   0.80   3.70
7                               Data for year 2022. 0.09   0.47   0.82   3.39
8                               Data for year 2023. 0.10   0.50   0.80   3.31
9                               Deceased.         0.00   0.14   1.36   4.47
10                              Female.           0.14   0.55   0.76   3.35
11                             General (gen); all patients. 0.14   0.55   0.76   3.35
12                              Hospitalized.     0.05   0.24   0.39   1.90
13                              Not hospitalized.  0.13   0.52   0.74   3.49
```

```
# Detecting which patients groups are NOT in pre2:
> setdiff(came.from.desc$came.from, pre2.summ$Group) # Give the names
[1] "fem.npr.res"      "fem.npr.sa.res"   "fem.pre.res"
[4] "mal.res"          "hos.fem.npr.sa.res" "hos.fem.pre.sa.res"
[7] "nho.fem.npr.sa.res" "nho.fem.pre.sa.res" "in.res"
[10] "to.res"           "se.res"           "ol.res"
```

In Box 5 (objects “pre2” and a summary in “pre2.summ”) we see that there is a total of 222 relevant results which include, as one of the variables involved “pregnancy”. Those results include 13 different patient’s groups –at which there are some pregnant woman, and thus, tables to be presented. In contrast, there are 12 groups where do not have tables for for “pregnancy”. These include the age groups of infants, toddlers, senior or old persons (“in.res”, “to.res”, “se.res” and “ol.res”). Also, groups that do not contain pregnant persons, say, the group formed exclusively by males, “mal.res”, and the groups formed by not pregnant females: “fem.npr.res”, “fem.npr.sa.res”, “hos.fem.npr.sa.res” and “nho.fem.npr.sa.res”.

There are other three groups that do not include “pregnancy” pairs, and those are the ones formed exclusively by pregnant woman, say, “fem.pre.res”, “hos.fem.pre.sa.res” and “nho.fem.pre.sa.res”. In those three groups all patients included are pregnant females, and thus not “pregnancy” contrast are possible.

Now, the problem is how to make sense of the 222 results found in the set “pre2”? We could employ a “*divide and conquer*” approach, i.e., divide the whole set of 222 rows into sub-sets that could be interpreted more easily. Box 6 present that approach, including lines of interpretation that begin with “# * Interpretation:”

```
# Box 6. Divide and conquer approach for pre2.

# Divide pre2 into two disjoint sets:
> pre2.or0 <- pre2[pre2$or == 0,] # Cases with odds ratio equal to zero
> pre2.orL0 <- pre2[pre2$or > 0,] # Cases with odds ratio larger than zero

# Analyze first pre2.or0.
# See main variables ordering by table name:
```

```

> pre2.or0 <- pre2.or0[order(pre2.or0$name.tab), ]
# Rename the rows
> attributes(pre2.or0)$row.names <- c(1:nrow(pre2.or0))
# See main variables:
> pre2.or0[, c(3:5, 10)]
      name.tab pv or came.from
1   deceased_pregnancy 1 0   ch.res
2     gender_pregnancy 1 0   ad.res
3     gender_pregnancy 1 0   ch.res
4     gender_pregnancy 1 0   ma.res
5     gender_pregnancy 1 0   te.res
6       icu_pregnancy 1 0   ch.res
7  intubated_pregnancy 1 0   ch.res
8 pregnancy_cardiovascular 1 0   ch.res
9     pregnancy_copd 1 0   ch.res
10    pregnancy_diabetes 1 0   ch.res

# A table; rows with each different name of table:
> table(pre2.or0$name.tab)

      deceased_pregnancy      gender_pregnancy      icu_pregnancy
                1                4                1
intubated_pregnancy pregnancy_cardiovascular      pregnancy_copd
                1                1                1
pregnancy_diabetes
                1

# Now let's see results for "deceased_pregnancy"
> present.table(pre2.or0[1,]) # See results for the first row ("deceased_pregnancy")

Results for table of variable "deceased" (in rows)
and variable "pregnancy" (in columns).
Suffix ".T" after the variable name means "TRUE", while ".F" means "FALSE".
The data came from selecting variables in group "ch.res".

Raw data:
      pregnancy.F pregnancy.T Total.Row
deceased.F 462,011      171    462,182
deceased.T   525         0        525
Total.Col  462,536      171    462,707

Expected values assuming independence:
      pregnancy.F pregnancy.T
deceased.F 462,011      171
deceased.T   525         0

Relative frequencies:
      pregnancy.F pregnancy.T Total.Row
deceased.F  0.99850    0.00037  0.99887
deceased.T  0.00113    0.00000  0.00113
Total.Col  0.99963    0.00037  1.00000

```

Conditional probabilities of row given column:

	pregnancy.F	pregnancy.T
deceased.F pregnancy	0.99886	1
deceased.T pregnancy	0.00114	0

Conditional probabilities of column given row:

	deceased.F	deceased.T
pregnancy.F deceased	0.99963	1
pregnancy.T deceased	0.00037	0

Results of Fisher's test for independence

Odds Ratio	p-value
0	1

Inverse of Odds Ratio, $1/(\text{Odds Ratio}) = \text{Inf}$

```
# * Interpretation: This case is in the group of children
# ("ch.res"; child (ch) from 5 to 12 years)
# even when there are 525 deceased in this group,
# none of those are pregnant (0 in cell),
# thus observed and expected values are identical,
# producing an odd value of zero.
```

```
# Now, in rows 2:5 we have the table "gender_pregnancy". In those 4 cases
# the row corresponding to "male" will be zero for both "pregnancy.F" and "pregnancy.T"
# see:
> present.table(pre2.or0[2,])
```

Results for table of variable "gender" (in rows)
and variable "pregnancy" (in columns).

Suffix ".T" after the variable name means "TRUE", while ".F" means "FALSE".
The data came from selecting variables in group "ad.res".

Raw data:

	pregnancy.F	pregnancy.T	Total.Row
female	6,060,538	251,192	6,311,730
male	0	0	0
Total.Col	6,060,538	251,192	6,311,730

Expected values assuming independence:

	pregnancy.F	pregnancy.T
female	6,060,538	251,192
male	0	0

Relative frequencies:

	pregnancy.F	pregnancy.T	Total.Row
female	0.9602	0.0398	1
male	0.0000	0.0000	0
Total.Col	0.9602	0.0398	1

Conditional probabilities of row given column:

	pregnancy.F	pregnancy.T
--	-------------	-------------

female pregnancy	1	1
male pregnancy	0	0

Conditional probabilities of column given row:

	female	male
pregnancy.F gender	0.9602	NaN
pregnancy.T gender	0.0398	NaN

Results of Fisher's test for independence

Odds Ratio	p-value
0	1

Inverse of Odds Ratio, $1/(\text{Odds Ratio}) = \text{Inf}$

```
# * Interpretation: For rows 2 to 5, all of them with "gender" (in rows)
# and variable "pregnancy" (in columns) we have the same interpretation:
# Those tables make no sense because males have 0 in both pregnancy
# categories.
```

```
# We only need to review
```

```
> pre2.or0[6:10, c(3:5, 10)] # Remaining rows
      name.tab pv or came.from
6      icu_pregnancy 1 0   ch.res
7      intubated_pregnancy 1 0   ch.res
8 pregnancy_cardiovascular 1 0   ch.res
9      pregnancy_copd 1 0   ch.res
10     pregnancy_diabetes 1 0   ch.res
```

```
# Note that all these are in the patient's group "ch.res", i.e.,
# child (ch) from 5 to 12 years.
```

```
# In all those cases there could be some pregnant females
# within that age group; let's see:
```

```
> present.table(pre2.or0[6,])
```

Results for table of variable "icu" (in rows)
and variable "pregnancy" (in columns).

Suffix ".T" after the variable name means "TRUE", while ".F" means "FALSE".
The data came from selecting variables in group "ch.res".

Raw data:

	pregnancy.F	pregnancy.T	Total.Row
icu.F	23,649	22	23,671
icu.T	793	0	793
Total.Col	24,442	22	24,464

Expected values assuming independence:

	pregnancy.F	pregnancy.T
icu.F	23,650	21
icu.T	792	1

Relative frequencies:

	pregnancy.F	pregnancy.T	Total.Row
icu.F	0.96669	9e-04	0.96759
icu.T	0.03241	0e+00	0.03241
Total.Col	0.99910	9e-04	1.00000

Conditional probabilities of row given column:

	pregnancy.F	pregnancy.T
icu.F pregnancy	0.96756	1
icu.T pregnancy	0.03244	0

Conditional probabilities of column given row:

	icu.F	icu.T
pregnancy.F icu	0.99907	1
pregnancy.T icu	0.00093	0

Results of Fisher's test for independence

Odds Ratio	p-value
0	1

Inverse of Odds Ratio, $1/(\text{Odds Ratio}) = \text{Inf}$

The following present only results up to the raw data tables
(you can see the full results repeating the commands)

```
> present.table(pre2.or0[7,])
```

Results for table of variable "intubated" (in rows)
and variable "pregnancy" (in columns).

Suffix ".T" after the variable name means "TRUE", while ".F" means "FALSE".
The data came from selecting variables in group "ch.res".

Raw data:

	pregnancy.F	pregnancy.T	Total.Row
intubated.F	23,703	22	23,725
intubated.T	739	0	739
Total.Col	24,442	22	24,464

```
> present.table(pre2.or0[8,])
```

Results for table of variable "pregnancy" (in rows)
and variable "cardiovascular" (in columns).

Suffix ".T" after the variable name means "TRUE", while ".F" means "FALSE".
The data came from selecting variables in group "ch.res".

Raw data:

	cardiovascular.F	cardiovascular.T	Total.Row
pregnancy.F	459,997	1,832	461,829
pregnancy.T	171	0	171
Total.Col	460,168	1,832	462,000

```
> present.table(pre2.or0[9,])
```

Results for table of variable "pregnancy" (in rows)
and variable "copd" (in columns).
Sufix ".T" after the variable name means "TRUE", while ".F" means "FALSE".
The data came from selecting variables in group "ch.res".

Raw data:

	copd.F	copd.T	Total.Row
pregnancy.F	461,588	265	461,853
pregnancy.T	171	0	171
Total.Col	461,759	265	462,024

```
> present.table(pre2.or0[10,])
```

Results for table of variable "pregnancy" (in rows)
and variable "diabetes" (in columns).
Sufix ".T" after the variable name means "TRUE", while ".F" means "FALSE".
The data came from selecting variables in group "ch.res".

Raw data:

	diabetes.F	diabetes.T	Total.Row
pregnancy.F	460,589	1,240	461,829
pregnancy.T	171	0	171
Total.Col	460,760	1,240	462,000

* Interpretation:

In all cases (rows 6 to 10 in pre2.or0) the number of persons
presenting the comorbidity and being pregnant is zero,
which in turn produces an odds ratio of zero.

We have analyzed the cases where or == 0, now
let's analyze the cases with odds ratio larger than zero:

```
> nrow(pre2.orL0)
```

```
[1] 212
```

Let's re-order by Odds Ratio (or) and rename rows.

```
> pre2.orL0 <- pre2.orL0[order(pre2.orL0$or),]
```

```
> attributes(pre2.orL0)$row.names <- c(1:212)
```

How many cases with or < 1?

```
> tapply(pre2.orL0$or, pre2.orL0$or<1, length)
```

```
FALSE TRUE
```

```
61 151
```

```
> summary(pre2.orL0[,4:5]) # Summaries of p-values and odds ratio
```

	pv	or
Min.	:0.00000	Min. :0.0010
1st Qu.:	0.00000	1st Qu.:0.2896
Median :	0.00000	Median :0.6180
Mean :	0.04525	Mean :1.0061
3rd Qu.:	0.00000	3rd Qu.:1.1239
Max. :	1.00000	Max. :7.7850

See the more extreme cases:

```
> head(pre2.orL0[, c(3:5, 10)], 5) # With the smallest or>0
```

	name.tab	pv	or	came.from
--	----------	----	----	-----------

```

1      pregnancy_copd  1.223728e-14 0.00100000  dec.res
2      pregnancy_copd  0.000000e+00 0.04582085  hos.res
3      deceased_pregnancy 0.000000e+00 0.04942971  hos.res
4      pregnancy_chr.renal 0.000000e+00 0.06072508  hos.res
5      pregnancy_hypertension 1.474020e-108 0.07025932  dec.res
> tail(pre2.orL0[, c(3:5, 10)], 5) # With the largest or>0 [in fact, or>1]
      name.tab      pv      or came.from
208  indigenous_pregnancy 0.000000e+00 5.042160  te.res
209  hospitalized_pregnancy 0.000000e+00 5.410045  te.res
210  indigenous_pregnancy 7.875995e-05 6.132834  ch.res
211  hospitalized_pregnancy 0.000000e+00 6.236660  ad.res
212  pregnancy_smoking 2.837254e-02 7.785024  ch.res

# How many cases of non-significant results? (pv > 0.01)
> nrow(pre2.orL0[pre2.orL0$pv>0.01, ])
[1] 21
> pre2.orL0[pre2.orL0$pv>0.01, c(3:5, 10)] # See main variables
      name.tab      pv      or came.from
87      pregnancy_obesity 1.00000000 0.5145891  ch.res
133     deceased_pregnancy 0.09568308 0.7324520  te.res
136     pos.cov2_pregnancy 0.16914891 0.7516606  ch.res
141     pregnancy_cardiovascular 0.03737351 0.7948375  te.res
142     pneumonia_pregnancy 1.00000000 0.8029220  ch.res
143     pregnancy_copd 0.19819506 0.8108247  ma.res
150     pregnancy_hypertension 0.07074254 0.9754205  ad.res
151     pregnancy_copd 0.85063350 0.9855957  ad.res
152     pneumonia_pregnancy 0.97566501 1.0005469  ma.res
153     pregnancy_copd 0.92234591 1.0127992  te.res
154     pregnancy_smoking 0.38598967 1.0454141  te.res
155     pregnancy_diabetes 0.44942124 1.0568651  te.res
158     deceased_pregnancy 0.06272186 1.0917077  ad.res
161     pregnancy_asthma 0.63332720 1.1331614  ch.res
162     icu_pregnancy 0.29439549 1.1385828  ma.res
175     pregnancy_imm.suppl 0.37894294 1.5272951  ch.res
177     pregnancy_other.com 0.43870101 1.6288763  ch.res
178     mexican_pregnancy 1.00000000 1.6581805  ch.res
195     pregnancy_hypertension 0.29176473 2.9153414  ch.res
196     pregnancy_chr.renal 0.29098201 2.9247247  ch.res
212     pregnancy_smoking 0.02837254 7.7850237  ch.res

# Note: All not significant cases came from an age group
> temp <- unique(pre2.orL0$came.from[pre2.orL0$pv>0.01])
> temp
[1] "ch.res" "te.res" "ma.res" "ad.res"
> came.from.desc$Description[is.element(came.from.desc$came.from, temp)]
[1] "Age group child (ch) from 5 to 12 years."
[2] "Age group teens (te) from 13 to 19 years."
[3] "Age group adult (ad) from 20 to 39 years."
[4] "Age group middle age (ma) from 40 to 59 years."

# We can now define the cases where:
# pv < 0.01 (isolate only "significant" cases),

```

```

# and from these segregate into two sets:
# pre3.smallOR (or < 1) and pre3.largeOR (or > 1)

> temp <- pre2.orL0[pre2.orL0$pv <= 0.01,] # Only significant at 0.01
> nrow(temp)
[1] 191
> pre3.smallOR <- temp[temp$or < 1,]
> pre3.largeOR <- temp[temp$or > 1,]
> nrow(pre3.smallOR)
[1] 143
> nrow(pre3.largeOR)
[1] 48

# Let's analyze first the smaller group of large OR (pre3.largeOR)
> head(pre3.largeOR[,c(3:5,11)])
      name.tab      pv      or      tab.file
156  mexican_pregnancy 5.592634e-04 1.090414      gen.tab
157  mexican_pregnancy 5.592634e-04 1.090414      fem.tab
159  mexican_pregnancy 6.453221e-03 1.122550 dpy2021.tab
160  pregnancy_other.com 2.045254e-05 1.128025 dpy2023.tab
163  pregnancy_imm.sup 3.792412e-05 1.157839      ad.tab
164  pregnancy_other.com 9.273667e-07 1.163932 dpy2022.tab

# We see that even when some cases of large OR are "significant"
# i.e., with an small p-value, that is due to the fact that we have very large
# sample sizes. We can be more strict, and consider only cases where
# the or > 2 because those will have more relevance. Thus let's make
# the group smaller:
> pre3.largeOR <- pre3.largeOR[pre3.largeOR$or>2,]
> nrow(pre3.largeOR)
[1] 26
> attributes(pre3.largeOR)$row.names <- c(1:26)
# And see the statistics for pv and or:
> summary(pre3.largeOR[,4:5])
      pv      or
Min.   :0.000e+00  Min.   :2.090
1st Qu.:0.000e+00  1st Qu.:2.742
Median :0.000e+00  Median :3.332
Mean   :4.766e-06  Mean   :3.451
3rd Qu.:0.000e+00  3rd Qu.:3.753
Max.   :7.876e-05  Max.   :6.237

# For brevity we will see the results of only the two more extremes cases
# (rows 1 and 26, with the smallest and larger odds ratios [larger than 2]).

> present.table(pre3.largeOR[1,])

Results for table of variable "pneumonia" (in rows)
and variable "pregnancy" (in columns).
Sufix ".T" after the variable name means "TRUE", while ".F" means "FALSE".
The data came from selecting variables in group "te.res".

```

Raw data:

	pregnancy.F	pregnancy.T	Total.Row
pneumonia.F	725,455	32,643	758,098
pneumonia.T	7,507	706	8,213
Total.Col	732,962	33,349	766,311

Expected values assuming independence:

	pregnancy.F	pregnancy.T
pneumonia.F	725,106	32,992
pneumonia.T	7,856	357

Relative frequencies:

	pregnancy.F	pregnancy.T	Total.Row
pneumonia.F	0.94668	0.04260	0.98928
pneumonia.T	0.00980	0.00092	0.01072
Total.Col	0.95648	0.04352	1.00000

Conditional probabilities of row given column:

	pregnancy.F	pregnancy.T
pneumonia.F pregnancy	0.98976	0.97883
pneumonia.T pregnancy	0.01024	0.02117

Conditional probabilities of column given row:

	pneumonia.F	pneumonia.T
pregnancy.F pneumonia	0.95694	0.91404
pregnancy.T pneumonia	0.04306	0.08596

Results of Fisher's test for independence

Odds Ratio	p-value
2.09005	0.00000

```
# * Interpretation: In teenagers (as in many other patients groups)
# pneumonia is a very relevant comorbidity. Here we see that in
# this age group the frequency of pneumonia in pregnant persons
# almost double the expected frequency, 706/357=1.977591
# producing a highly significant odds ratio larger than 2.
```

```
> present.table(pre3.largeOR[26,])
```

Results for table of variable "hospitalized" (in rows)

and variable "pregnancy" (in columns).

Suffix ".T" after the variable name means "TRUE", while ".F" means "FALSE".

The data came from selecting variables in group "ad.res".

Raw data:

	pregnancy.F	pregnancy.T	Total.Row
hospitalized.F	5,947,446	224,565	6,172,011
hospitalized.T	113,092	26,627	139,719
Total.Col	6,060,538	251,192	6,311,730

Expected values assuming independence:

	pregnancy.F	pregnancy.T
--	-------------	-------------

```
hospitalized.F 5,926,379      245,632
hospitalized.T  134,159        5,560
```

Relative frequencies:

```
                pregnancy.F pregnancy.T Total.Row
hospitalized.F  0.94228      0.03558  0.97786
hospitalized.T  0.01792      0.00422  0.02214
Total.Col       0.96020      0.03980  1.00000
```

Conditional probabilities of row given column:

```
                pregnancy.F pregnancy.T
hospitalized.F | pregnancy  0.98134    0.894
hospitalized.T | pregnancy  0.01866    0.106
```

Conditional probabilities of column given row:

```
                hospitalized.F hospitalized.T
pregnancy.F | hospitalized  0.96362    0.80942
pregnancy.T | hospitalized  0.03638    0.19058
```

Results of Fisher's test for independence

```
Odds Ratio   p-value
  6.23666     0.00000
```

```
# * Interpretation: From the previous results we see that there is
# a positive relation between pregnancy and hospitalization in
# the group of adults. The observed number of pregnant persons
# that were hospitalized, 26,627 is almost five times larger than
# the expected number, 5,560 if these two variables were independent:
# 26627/5560 = 4.789029 The difference gives a highly significant
# odds ratio larger than six.
```

```
# Now we are going to analyze the cases with small OR: "pre3.smallOR"
```

```
> summary(pre3.smallOR[,4:5])
```

```
      pv          or
Min.   :0.000e+00  Min.   :0.0010
1st Qu.:0.000e+00  1st Qu.:0.2272
Median :0.000e+00  Median :0.3947
Mean   :7.408e-05  Mean   :0.4235
3rd Qu.:0.000e+00  3rd Qu.:0.6253
Max.   :4.632e-03  Max.   :0.8836
```

```
# As before, we will reduce this group to isolate the more relevant
# results. Because we are dealing with or < 1, we will consider only cases
# with or < 0.5 (more extreme)
```

```
> pre3.smallOR <- pre3.smallOR[pre3.smallOR$or<0.5,]
```

```
> nrow(pre3.smallOR)
```

```
[1] 85
```

```
# See the two tails of this data.frame:
```

```
> head(pre3.smallOR[,c(3:5, 11)])
```

```
      name.tab          pv          or tab.file
1 pregnancy_copd 1.223728e-14 0.00100000 dec.tab
2 pregnancy_copd 0.000000e+00 0.04582085 hos.tab
```

```

3   deceased_pregnancy 0.000000e+00 0.04942971 hos.tab
4   pregnancy_chr.renal 0.000000e+00 0.06072508 hos.tab
5   pregnancy_hypertension 1.474020e-108 0.07025932 dec.tab
6   pregnancy_hypertension 0.000000e+00 0.08893523 hos.tab
> tail(pre3.smallOR[,c(3:5, 11)])
      name.tab          pv          or      tab.file
80 pregnancy_hypertension 6.253701e-124 0.4536794      ma.tab
81   pregnancy_obesity 1.575911e-304 0.4659767 dpy2020.tab
82   pregnancy_imm.sup 4.214172e-33 0.4734874 dpy2022.tab
83   pregnancy_smoking 2.744937e-86 0.4794032   hos.tab
84   pregnancy_imm.sup 1.483569e-37 0.4869923 dpy2023.tab
85   pregnancy_chr.renal 5.028686e-61 0.4927607   ad.tab

```

```

# As before, and for brevity we will present here only the two
# more extreme cases.

```

```

> present.table(pre3.smallOR[1,]) # The smallest or

```

```

Results for table of variable "pregnancy" (in rows)
and variable "copd" (in columns).

```

```

Sufix ".T" after the variable name means "TRUE", while ".F" means "FALSE".
The data came from selecting variables in group "dec.res".

```

```

Raw data:

```

	copd.F	copd.T	Total.Row
pregnancy.F	174,054	10,864	184,918
pregnancy.T	545	0	545
Total.Col	174,599	10,864	185,463

```

Expected values assuming independence:

```

	copd.F	copd.T
pregnancy.F	174,086	10,832
pregnancy.T	513	32

```

Relative frequencies:

```

	copd.F	copd.T	Total.Row
pregnancy.F	0.93848	0.05858	0.99706
pregnancy.T	0.00294	0.00000	0.00294
Total.Col	0.94142	0.05858	1.00000

```

Conditional probabilities of row given column:

```

	copd.F	copd.T
pregnancy.F copd	0.99688	1
pregnancy.T copd	0.00312	0

```

Conditional probabilities of column given row:

```

	pregnancy.F	pregnancy.T
copd.F pregnancy	0.94125	1
copd.T pregnancy	0.05875	0

```

Results of Fisher's test for independence

```

```

Odds Ratio    p-value

```

0.001 0.000

Inverse of Odds Ratio, $1/(\text{Odds Ratio}) = 1000$

* Interpretation: This table shows results in the group of

deceased persons:

```
> came.from.desc[came.from.desc$came.from=="dec.res", ]
```

```
  came.from n.res Description
13  dec.res  137  Deceased.
```

and the observed number of pregnant persons that presented

copd was zero, while the number expected under the hypothesis

of independence was 34, producing an or=0 that (for practical reasons)

was recorded as 0.001 in the data.frame all.res.

```
> present.table(pre3.smallOR[85,]) # The largest or (but still smaller than 0.5)
```

Results for table of variable "pregnancy" (in rows)

and variable "chr.renal" (in columns).

Suffix ".T" after the variable name means "TRUE", while ".F" means "FALSE".

The data came from selecting variables in group "ad.res".

Raw data:

	chr.renal.F	chr.renal.T	Total.Row
pregnancy.F	6,028,905	21,439	6,050,344
pregnancy.T	250,529	439	250,968
Total.Col	6,279,434	21,878	6,301,312

Expected values assuming independence:

	chr.renal.F	chr.renal.T
pregnancy.F	6,029,337	21,007
pregnancy.T	250,097	871

Relative frequencies:

	chr.renal.F	chr.renal.T	Total.Row
pregnancy.F	0.95677	0.00340	0.96017
pregnancy.T	0.03976	0.00007	0.03983
Total.Col	0.99653	0.00347	1.00000

Conditional probabilities of row given column:

	chr.renal.F	chr.renal.T
pregnancy.F chr.renal	0.9601	0.97993
pregnancy.T chr.renal	0.0399	0.02007

Conditional probabilities of column given row:

	pregnancy.F	pregnancy.T
chr.renal.F pregnancy	0.99646	0.99825
chr.renal.T pregnancy	0.00354	0.00175

Results of Fisher's test for independence

Odds Ratio	p-value
0.49276	0.00000

Inverse of Odds Ratio, $1/(\text{Odds Ratio}) = 2.02938$

```

# * Interpretation: This results are for the group "ad.res"

> came.from.desc[came.from.desc$came.from=="ad.res", ]
  came.from n.res      Description
22  ad.res   190 Age group adult (ad) from 20 to 39 years.

# involving the variables "pregnancy" and "chr.renal",

> var.desc[var.desc$Name=="chr.renal",]
  Name Abbr   Category
3 chr.renal  ch Comorbidity

                                     Description
3 logical; patient reported to be suffering chronic renal problems.

# While the observed number of pregnant persons with "chr.renal"
# is 439, the expected value of this cell under independence is 871,
# i.e., almost half: 439/871 = 0.5040184 resulting in a significant
# odds ratio 0.49276 This means that in the group of adults the
# observed number of pregnant persons with the disease is
# well below the expected value.
-----

```

We have seen how taking a single variable, "pregnancy", of the 20 ones available we can find relevant information on the results contained in this package. Given the large sample size of the original data, *p*-values ("pv" in this package) are in many of the cases very small, close or equal to zero, thus we can be "almost sure" that those relations presented real associations between the variables with an odds ratio ("or" in this package) different to 1. However, it is always important to see if the relation was direct (or > 1) or inverse (or < 1). Furthermore, the user must keep in mind that "correlation does not imply causation", and thus cause-and-effect relationships need to be carefully examined on the light of clinical or other medical knowledge before being claimed.

In (Martínez, 2023) we present networks of variables from this data using different groups of patients and thresholds of odds ratios. Such graphs can be obtained from the data in this package. Briefly, from "all.res" you can isolate the data of a particular patient's group (variable "came.from") which fulfills a desired odds ratio threshold (use variable "or2" to take into account both, direct and indirect relations). Then the R package "igraph" (Csardi and Nepusz, 2006) can be employed to draw the graph, adjusting the parameters to present an easy to interpret network.

REFERENCES

- Csardi G and Nepusz T (2006) The igraph software package for complex network research. *InterJournal, Complex Systems*, 1695. URL <https://igraph.org>.
- Martínez O (2023) Associations between variables in a cohort of Mexican Covid-19 patients. *Currently in preparation; not submitted yet*, 1, 1–5.
- McHugh ML (2009) The odds ratio: calculation, usage, and interpretation. *Biochemia medica*, 19, 120–126.
- R Core Team (2022) R: A language and environment for statistical computing. URL <https://www.R-project.org/>.